

Original Article

Corporate Social Responsibility Activities for Mid-Day Meals: A Study of JSW Steel Limited in Ballari

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Abstract:

This Study examine the Corporate Social Responsivity (CSR) activities of Jindal South West (JSW) Steel Limited in the Ballari district of Karnataka, focusing on the mid-day meal program implemented in partner with the Akshay Patra Foundation. The mid-day meal scheme, one of the largest school feeding programs in the region, aim to hunger eradication, and encourage school attendance among children in 44 rural schools. The program benefits approximately 1.5 lakh students daily benefited, providing nutritious meals and ensuring improved focus and concentration in the classroom environment. This research investigates the effectiveness of the mid-day meals scheme, evaluation students' satisfaction regarding meal quality, hygiene, and its impact on academic performance. The study utilised both primary and secondary data collection methods, including surveys, observations, and review of status, attendance and academic performance of students, highlighting the importance of CSR initiatives in fostering social welfare and contribution to educational development. The study concludes by emphasizing the significant role of corporate involvement in addressing food insecurity and promoting educational equity in underserved communities.

Key Words: Section 135, companies Act 2013, CSR, Hungry eradication, Mid-day meals, students' satisfaction, academic performance.

Introduction

Jindal South West (JSW) Steel Limited, a prominent private Steel manufacturer in India, has actively engaged in Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) activities to support mid-day meal programs in the Ballari district of Karnataka. Corporate Social Responsibility has become a powerful tool for managing social and economic challenges in India. Mid-day meals are provided by the JSW Foundation has Collaboration with the Akshaya Patra Foundation. Forty-four villages' schools are beneficiaries of the hungry eradication program under Section 135, the companies Act 2013, thereby contributing to the educational institution of society. Six mobile vans serve food from kitchen centre to different local school centres at the right time. The mid-day meal scheme is one of the largest schools feeding programs arounds in its operational area, improving nutritional standards among school children and promoting school attendance. The involvement of the Akshaya Patra foundation through CSR activities has significantly enhanced the reach and impact of the mid-day meal program, effectively addressing challenges such as food insecurity and child malnutrition. The company serves 1.5 lakh school children's hot meals, nutritious meals every day, supporting the provision of mid-day meals in 44 rural schools.

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The company encourages children to attend school, and these mid-day meals help prevent them from dropping out. The company aim to avoid classroom hunger, increase school enrolment and attendance, and address malnutrition. Encouraging a child belonging to disadvantaged section to attend school more regularly and helping them concentrate on classroom activities.

Literature Review

Sreenath Menon, M.D. Sangeetha (2013)¹ studied that mid-day meal scheme in India is the largest free school lunch program. In 2021, the scheme was renamed as Pradhan Mantri Poshan Shakti Nirman. A study was conducted to quantify the routine daily dietary intake of school children with reference to calorie and protein intake. They selected five government schools of urban area of Bengaluru and collected a samples size of 345 students. They used a structured questionnaire.

Chandra Shekhar Sahai (2014)² indicated that the Mid-Day Meal scheme was launched by the Government of India with the aim of universalising of primary education and increase enrolment especially of children belonging to weaker section of the society. He discussed many problems in the implementation of this scheme. A major drawback found in this scheme was the insufficient basic infrastructure in schools. Parents, panchayats directed all states to provide cooked meals to all primary school children. The death of 23 children due to poisoned food served to them under the Mid-Day Meals raised question marks.

Anbu Arumugam (2013)³ reveals that despite primary schooling being universally recognised as a driver of economic growth. He studied India's population and found that number of illiterate people was higher than in any other country, according to 2011 Census of India. The company's social protection programme is essential for ensuring access to food and addressing the problem of malnutrition. Mid-day meals are one of the initiatives aimed at improving the level of nutrition.

Nidhi Sinha (2019)⁴ Understanding the higher degree of undernourishment among school going children, the Mid-Day Meal Programme was launched in India in 1995. This the research paper focuses on Mid-Day Meal programme across states, within states, and among income social groups. The study also examines the relationship between mid-day meals and school infrastructure.

Objectives of the study

1. To understand the hunger eradication program for poor students in government, Aided, private schools by JSW Steel Limited in Ballari.
2. To offer findings and suggestions.

Research Methodology: It refers to the systematic, theoretical analyses of the methods and techniques used to collect, analysis and interpret data in research. This methodology is applied to study the mid-day meals provided by JSW Steel Limited.

Data Collection Methods

There are two methods of data collection, namely

1. Primary Data Collection:

- a) Descriptive Survey: - Gathered data on the number of students benefiting from mid-day meals programs provided by JSW Steel Limited
- b) Quantitative Surveys: Used structured questions to asks students about their satisfaction with mid-day meals to gather numerical data using a Likert scale.
- c) Observations: - conducted schools visits to observe children meal quality, hygiene, and distribution processes.

2. Secondary Data Collection:

- a. Reviewed JSW Steel Limited reports and CSR documents on mid -Day meals
- b. Reviewed journals, books and research papers related to mid-day meal schemes.

3. Sampling Techniques

- a. Population: Students who benefit from mid -day meals provided by JSW Steel Limited
- b. Sample Size: Four schools were covered, with a total of 194 to 196 are student respondents.

4. Data Analysis Methods

Quantitative Data:

- a. Use statistical tools, such as Excel, to analysis survey response
- b. Calculate percentages, and satisfaction scores.
- c. Represent findings using bar charts.

Limitation of the study

CSR activities for Mid-Day Meals provided by JSW Steel Limited in Ballari District, Karnataka. The study includes beneficiaries from selected school around its operational area. The response from students regarding satisfaction and meals quality were collected. Beneficiaries' information was taken from 2017-18 to 2023-24, Measuring the impact of the meals on academic performance or health could present challenges in determining clear outcomes.

Scope of the study

This study focuses on evaluating the impact of the mid-day meal program initiated by JSW Steel Limited as part of its CSR activities. It examines the experiences and satisfaction levels of student beneficiaries, focusing on the quality, nutritional value, and adequacy of the meals provided. Student satisfaction regarding the meals. Nutritional impact of the meals on students' health. Influence of the program on students' academic performance, alternance and overall well-being.

Importance of the study

The study highlights how the mid-day meal program contributes to reducing malnutrition and improving the overall health of students in the Ballari District of Karnataka. Enhanced academic performance, increased school attendance, reducing the financial burden on low-income families, the mid-day meal program promotes equity and access to education for underprivileged students.

Figure No.01: Number of students benefiting from mid-day meals provided by JSW Steel Limited.

Year	Numbers of beneficiaries	% of Beneficiaries
2017-18	1,15,000	18%
2018-19	1,01,000	14%
2019-20	1,20,000	18%
2020-21	20,000	03%
2021-22	40,000	06%
2022-23	1,30,000	21%
2023-24	1,25,000	20%
Total	6,51,001	100%

Source: Data from JSW Foundation

The above table reveals that the large number of students beneficiaries were recorded during the 2022-23 academic year, with around 44 schools benefitting from the quality meals provided by JSW Steel Limited. In contrast, a significantly lower numbers of students' beneficiaries i.e., 20,000 were recorded during year 2020-21 due to disruption caused by Covid-19 Pandemic. After covid 19 pandemic, the number of beneficiaries gradually increased during the year 2021-22 and 2022-23

Figure No.02: Number of respondents regarding the cleanliness and hygiene of the dining area where mid-day meals are served by JSW Steel Limited.

Sl. No	Satisfaction level	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
01	Very Poor	19	10%
02	Poor	12	06%
03	Average	6	03%
04	Good	42	21%
05	Excellent	117	60%
	Grand Total	196	100%

Source: Field survey conducted selected school

Interpretation

The above table indicates that numbers of respondents regarding the cleanliness and hygiene of the dining area where mid-day meals are served by JSW Steel Limited. 10% respondents rated the cleanliness and hygiene as very poor. 6% rated it as poor, and 3 % rated it as average. 21% of respondents rated the cleanliness and hygiene as good, and finally, majority, 60%, rated it as excellent.

Figure No.03: Number of respondents were satisfied with quality meals provided by JSW Steel Limited

Sl. No	Satisfaction level	No. of respondents	% of Respondents
01	Very satisfied	41	22%
02	Dissatisfied	5	02%
03	Neutral	8	04%
04	Satisfied	29	15%
05	Very satisfied	111	57%
	Grand Total	194	100%

Source: Field survey conducted selected school

Interpretation

The above table shows the numbers of respondents who were satisfied with the quality of meals provided by JSW Steel Limited. The data from the survey shows the following satisfaction levels regarding the quality of meals. 22% of respondents were very satisfied with the quality of meals. 2% were dissatisfied. 4 % were neutral. 15% were satisfied. The majority, 57% were very satisfied

Figure No.04: Number of respondents regarding their ability to concentrate in the classroom after meals served by JSW Steel Limited.

Sl. No	Concentration level in classroom	No. of Respondents	% of respondents
01	Very poor	10	05%
02	Poor	10	05%
03	Average	38	19%
04	Good	67	35%
05	Excellent	69	36%
	Grand Total	194	100%

Source: Field survey conducted selected school

The above table indicates that students' concentration in the classroom after lunch is rated as excellent by the highest percentages of respondents (36%). The Smallest percentages 5%, rated it as poor and very poor.

Findings

1. The highest number of mid-day meal beneficiaries was recorded in 2022-23 (1,30,000 students), accounting for 21 % of the total beneficiaries. The lowest number of beneficiaries was observed in 2020-21 (20,000 Students), contribution to only 3% of the total, likely due to the impact of the Covid -19 pandemic and associated school closure.
2. The majority of respondents (60%) rated the cleanliness and hygiene of the dining area as excellent. A Combined 16% of respondents expressed dissatisfaction, with 10% rating it as very poor and 6% rating it as poor.
3. 57% of respondents were very satisfied with the quality of the meals, making it the highest satisfaction level. Only 2% of respondents were dissatisfied with the meals, indicating negative feedback.
4. Significant portion of respondents, 71% (35% good +36% excellent), reported that they were able to concentrate well in the classroom after meals. Only 10% of respondents rated their concentration as poor or very poor.

Suggestions

1. It is recommended that JSW Steel Limited explore strategies to increase student participation and ensure the continuity of meal programs, especially during times of crisis, to mitigate the impact of disruptions such as the Covid-19 pandemic
2. Improvement in cleanliness and maintenance of the dining area should be prioritised by JSW Steel Limited.
3. An improve overall satisfaction, enhance the taste of the meals, as 2% of respondents expressed dissatisfaction
4. Ensure consistent nutrition and improve the taste of the food provided by JSW Steel Limited to enhance overall satisfaction and concentration among the students.

Conclusion

Mid-day meal program provided by JSW Steel Limited has significantly, impacted students, as evidenced by the data. The number of student beneficiaries peaked in the 2022-23 academic year with around 130,000, reflecting the program reach despite the setback during the Covid-19 pandemic. Post pandemic, the number of beneficiaries gradually increased, showing a steady recovery. In terms of satisfaction, the cleanliness and hygiene of the dining area, student concentration were rated positively by most respondents, with 60% rating it as excellent. Similarly, the quality of meals was highly appreciated, with 57% of respondents being very satisfies. JSW steel Limited mid-day meal initiatives has made a substantial difference in the students lives, offering nutrition meals but also enhancing the overall learning environment.

Reference:

1. **Sreenath Menon, M.D. Sangeetha (2013)**¹Contribution of mid-day meal scheme to students' nutrition in Bengaluru. International Journals of Community Medicine and Public health, 10, 2013.
2. **Chandra Shekhar Sahai (2014)**²Mid-Day Meal scheme was launched by the Government of India. International Journal of Humanities and Social Science invention, ISSN No:2319-7722, Volume No:3 Issue 10, Pp.6-9
3. **Anbu Arumugam (2016)** Sustainable development goals and India-A Study towards the sustainability of Noon meal Scheme in India. IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science, Volume 21, Issue 8, Pp 48-56, e-ISSN:2279-0837.
4. **Nidhi Sinha (2019)**⁴Mid-day meals: A detailed study of Indian states, IJRAR, International Journals, Volume No: 06, Issue No: 02, E-ISSN No:2348-1269
5. **Business Ethic** by S.K Bhatia
6. **Corporate Social Responsibility** by Sanjay Agrawal